

STUDY OF ATTENTION IN PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGY

Ismatillayeva Sarvinoz Baxtiyor qizi¹,

Mamataliyeva Durdona Hamdamovna²

Termiz State University, Faculty of Social Sciences,

3rd level students of Applied Psychology

<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejsspc-v03-i02-p1-31>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 03rd February 2023

Accepted: 13th February 2023

Online: 14th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Attention, imagination, active, passive, psychology, pedagogy, apperception, concentration, feeling, cognitive activity.

ABSTRACT

Attention is very important in human life. It is a necessary condition for the implementation of any activity. It is the attention that completely executes all our mental processes; only attention allows us to perceive the world around us. But attention is not the only requirement for successful activity. It can also tell a lot about the general structure of personality, a person's social orientation. Attention is one of the important conditions for the successful implementation of all types of human activities and their effectiveness. The more complex, laborious, and long-term a person's work is, the higher the conditions and requirements for attention. A person's intelligence, prudence, quick perception, thoroughness, kindness serve as an important factor in his living conditions and interpersonal relations. Attention is involved in all types of mental activity, human actions also take place with its participation. It should be emphasized that attention is not a separate mental process like intuition, perception, memory, thinking, imagination, speech. Therefore, it participates in all mental processes, affects their productivity. Therefore, objects focused on are clearly reflected at the point of concentration of consciousness. So, attention is the internal activity of a person that ensures the quality, productivity and efficiency of mental processes. It is also a necessary condition for any human activity.

Relevance of the topic: Attention is of great importance in human life. It is a necessary condition for the implementation of any activity. It is the attention that completes all our mental processes, only attention allows us to perceive the world around us. But focus is not the only requirement for successful activity. It can also tell a lot about the general structure of personality, a person's social orientation. The problem of attention is traditionally considered one of the most important and complex problems of scientific psychology.

The purpose of the research: to study the place and characteristics of the concept of attention in pedagogical psychology. Studying the mental activity of people through attention.

Materials and methods of investigation: Attention is the attraction of the subject's activity to an object or event. It is a necessary condition for the effectiveness of any conscious activity. Optimal sources of excitation in specific areas of the cerebral cortex form the physiological basis of Attention. Attention is divided into two types: involuntary (passive) attention and voluntary (active) attention. Such attention does not require willpower from a person. The power of the stimulus is of great importance to attract attention; for example, the beauty, brightness, pungent smell and other properties of the object attract attention involuntarily. In voluntary attention, mental activity is consciously attracted to a specific object with a predetermined goal. This type of focus requires willpower. That is why this focus is also called volitional focus. The entire conscious activity of a person is mainly carried out by means of voluntary attention. The scope of attention is determined by the number of things that he can fit into his scope in the shortest time (as if at once). In this sense, Attention can be broad or narrow. Generally, a broad Focus is a good Focus. The scope of attention depends on the task and nature of the perceived objects and the activity of the person perceiving them. The study of the problem of attention is reflected in the works of I. V. Strakhov. Below we will focus on their main essence. A person has a social nature according to the origin of attention and the way of working. It is the cause of people's professional activity and is considered one of the main psychological components of the labor process. The most important sign of attention is the concentration of a person's psyche in the process of activity and in communication with others. Characteristics of attention studied in psychology are reflected in various qualities and development. Concentration in serial relations has two types: it is selectively directed to objects and events, that is, the conscious separation of the object of attention, at the same time it forms a system of acts by means of distraction from many other objects. planning is focused on the subject of work, but its process is also an object of attention. Concentration is directed to the object of activity and movement with it. Psychologists define attention as a mental process characterized by focusing and focusing the human mind on any event, object or activity. What is meant by directionality? It is an item selection among many other things. Concentration refers to the ability of a person not to be distracted from the chosen topic by others who are not related to him.

This is attention. Specific features of attention help a person to successfully act in the external environment and ensure its fuller and more accurate reflection in spiritual reality. The object on which a person's attention is focused occupies a central place in the mind, everything else is vaguely and weakly perceived by a person. But the main features of attention show that the person can change and different objects occupy a central place in the mind. Attention is a dependent cognitive process, because we cannot observe it outside of other mental phenomena. A person can listen, think, do, look attentively or attentively. In this regard, attention is only a characteristic of other cognitive processes. In psychology, two more characteristics of attention are attention and inattention. Basically, we can say that these are two aspects of the same property. From childhood, the child is taught to do everything carefully, and over time, attention becomes a permanent characteristic of a person - attention. People with this characteristic show themselves in society only from a positive side. This

feature also comes with the ability to observe, to better perceive the environment. A careful person is distinguished by a quick reaction to ongoing events and deeper experience, good learning ability. Mindfulness is related to the effective development of a process such as attention. The characteristics of attention (ie, volume, concentration, stability, distribution) help to develop the above characteristic qualitatively. Such a person does not have problems with concentration or involuntary attention. Psychologists say that interest plays a big role in work or study. It is easier for a cautious person to mobilize his forces if there is no interest in the matter. It is difficult to combine any mental activity with constant efforts to maintain focus. Therefore, working under conditions of voluntary attention is not always effective. The deepest concentration, concentration, is possible only with voluntary attention. To move from voluntary attention to post-voluntary attention, the work itself must be activated. This can be done with the help of memory work - understanding and the law of interest. However, when we work, we often get distracted. Is it possible to get rid of unnecessary distractions, learn to work with concentration? For this, you need to know some rules of concentrated work. Functions of attention:

1. Describing attention as a complex mental phenomenon, a number of functions of attention are distinguished. The essence of attention is manifested, first of all, in the important, relevant, that is, in the choice. needs, the effects associated with this activity and other - insignificant, side, competitive effects that are ignored (slow down, eliminate).
2. Behavior, cognitive activity until the goal is achieved. One of the most important functions of attention is to regulate and control the flow of activity. Complex processes such as expectation, attitude, apperception are also related to attention events. Therefore, we can talk about a certain role of attention in the expectation of reality.
3. Attention can also be manifested in emotional and mnemonic, mental and action processes. Sensory attention is associated with the perception of different modality (type) stimuli. In this regard, visual and auditory emotional attention is distinguished. The most studied emotional focus. Through extensive research, we've learned 5 key focus techniques: First, remember that not all distractions are bad. Deep concentration of attention is accompanied by the stimulation of certain areas of the cerebral cortex. However, it is impossible to maintain excitement for a long time - fatigue appears. Therefore, in a number of cases, distractions are justified - when they are in the nature of a short-term rest that enhances concentration. For such a rest, 5-10 minutes per hour of mental work is enough (a few physical exercises, a little self- self-massage, eye gymnastics, etc.). However, the greatest inconvenience is brought to us by involuntary distractions during the work process: extraneous thoughts unrelated to it, the desire to look at extraneous things. Therefore, the second rule is the need to create an environment that matches the nature of the work. Some people can work with concentration in any conditions, but for many external factors are very important: relative silence, order at the table, good lighting, comfortable position, etc. Pure mental ability to work in such conditions is also important. Therefore, for example, it is very easy to concentrate in the library. A useful and predetermined attitude to work. Thirdly, it should be taken into account that concentration increases under the influence of small side stimuli. There is no need to strive to work in complete silence: a small sound background (quiet music, noise outside the window, birdsong) is still necessary. The experience of one of

the libraries in London is widely known, in which completely soundproof places were created for readers. It soon became clear that concentrated work is impossible in complete silence. Fourth, you should focus on the most favorable periods for mental work during the day. According to many experiences, the peak of our activity is at 5, 11, 16.20 and 24 hours. It is easier to achieve maximum concentration during these periods.

Conclusion: If we consider the basics of attention, it can be noted that it is the product of the most complex development. The arbitrariness of personal attention is of particular importance, and its formation opens the way to understanding the internal mechanisms of the complex form of organization of human conscious activity, which reveals a decisive role in all his mental activities. To improve vital functions, developing attention is as important as training any other physiological parameters of the body. Attention is focused on a more accurate perception of the picture of the world, solving mental tasks, as well as choosing the most important factors of human activity. Therefore, we need to know exactly how to train attention to maintain your psychological state.

References:

1. Nemov R.S.: Psychology: a textbook for students. higher. ped. institutions: 3 kn. - 4th edition.-M .: humanist. ed. center VLADOS, 2001.- Book 1: general foundations of psychology.- 688 p.
2. General psychology: A textbook for students. in-tov // Ed. A. V. Petrovsky. - 3rd Edition, Revised. and supplement - M .: Education, 1986 .-- 463 p
3. E. Goziyev general psychology Study guide for psychology major II - book
4. <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caution>
5. <https://mywordworld.ru/uz/children/izuchenie-osobennostei-vnimanija-vnimanie---ponyatie-vidy-osobennosti/>
6. <https://apriori-nauka.ru/uz/management/sushchnost-i-funksii-vnimaniya-ponyatie-i-sushchnost-vnimaniya.html>